

EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION TOWARDS SPS CHILLING CENTER: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

M. Pavithran*, Dr. K. Binith Muthukrishnan & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Pavithran, Dr. K. Binith Muthukrishnan & Dr. B. Velmurugan, "Employee Job Satisfaction Towards SPS Chilling Center: An Analytical Study", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 57-59, 2023.

Abstract:

The study examines different aspects of job satisfaction like culture, leadership communication, commitment, job content, training, rewards and recognition opportunities, teamwork, superior subordinate relationship and delegation, at SPS Chilling Center. The research done is descriptive study involving survey and enquiry. The tools used for the data collection are questionnaires interviews and observations. The sampling design used is random sampling Sample of 100 employees from study population of 210 was taken. The secondary was collected from the company's manuals, employee handbook, BTPS intranet and website. The research was carried out for a period of 2 months. The analysis was carried on a software SPSS and stated satisfaction level of different parameters. The overall job satisfaction showed people were satisfied with their current job but still measures should to be taken to improve the satisfaction level.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Job Content, Teamwork, Commitment.

About SPS Chilling Center:

Registered in 2016 India SPS Chilling Center has gained immense expertise in supplying & trading of Air chiller etc. The supplier company is located in Dindigul, Tamil Nadu and is one of the leading sellers of listed products. Buy Air chiller in bulk from us for the best quality products and service.

Significance of the Study:

Attitudes are evaluative statements either favorable or unfavorable - concerning objects, people or events. They reflect how one feels about something. Work Attitudes are the feelings and beliefs that largely determine how employees will perceive their environment, commit themselves to intended actions, and ultimately behave. Job Satisfaction is one of the many work related attitudes individuals hold like Job Involvement, Organizational Commitment, etc. Job Satisfaction thus is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings and emotions with which employees view their work. A person with high level of job satisfaction holds positive feelings about the job, while a person who is dissatisfied with his/ her job holds negative feelings about the job. Job satisfaction is an important concern for both the employee as well as the employer as it has an impact on many organizational behaviours. The employees satisfaction is conducted to provide the information needed to improve various factors like productivity loyalty and job satisfaction. With the employee's views, organizations can identify the root causes and create improvements. Organization just needs to discover what motivates the people, what drives loyalty and what genuinely makes the employees happy and employee remain satisfied only when they know their issued are being addressed.

Measuring Job Satisfaction:

There are many methods for measuring job satisfaction. By far, the most common method for collecting data regarding employee job satisfaction is the Likert scale (named after Rensis Likert). Other less common methods of for gauging job satisfaction include: Yes/No questions, True/False questions, point systems, checklist, forced choice answers. The Job Descriptive Index (JDI), created by smith, Kendall, & Hulin (1969), job satisfaction that has been widely used. It measures one's satisfaction in five facets: pay, promotions and opportunities, coworkers, supervision, and the work itself. The scale is simple, participants answer either yes, no, or decide in response to whether given statements accurately describe one job. The Job in General Index is an overall measurement of job satisfaction. It was an improvement to the job Descriptive Index because the JDI focused too much on individual facets and not enough on work satisfaction in general.

Relative Factors Involved in Job Satisfaction:

- Nature of work
- Working Environment
- Working hours
- Job security
- Responsibility given for the job
- Relationship with colleagues
- Relationship with supervisors
- Safety measures
- Grievance handling
- Wage rate system
- Incentives
- Canteen facilities

- Bonus schemes
- Family welfare measures
- Medical / First Aid facilities
- Recognition
- Rewards

Review of Literature:

Zahariishak et. al (2017) This study examines the predictions on sexual harassment experience towards job satisfaction and work stress among female employees at three universities in the Klang Valley, Malaysia. A questionnaire consisting of four sections has been used for this research. The four sections measured sexual harassment experience, job satisfaction, work stress and respondents information. A total of 1423 participants were selected through simple random sampling technique.

Yuan-Ho Chen (2018) Research study on Employee's satisfaction and happiness of companies with different cultural managements had revealed many interesting and significant outcome. Survey questionnaires exquisitely designed and specialized in employee's satisfaction, happiness and job commitment were used and focused in this study.

Garazi Azanza et. al (2019) The promotion of a flexibility-oriented organizational culture, based on support and innovation, may provide a great value in today's competitive economy. This type of organizational culture may be a breeding ground for authentic leadership, which, in turn, has positive effects on employees' attitudes. This study examines how flexibility-oriented organizational cultures facilitate positive outcomes at the employee level through its impact on authentic leadership. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data from 571 employees belonging to several Spanish private organizations. The results show that authentic leadership partially mediates the positive relationship between flexibility-oriented organizational cultures and employees' job satisfaction.

Mohammad Hosein Lotfi et. al (2020) This study is analyzing the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction among the employees of Tehran Payame Noor University. Statistical Society of this study includes all personnel of the organization (800 people) in 2012 and the sample size includes 260 people that were selected randomly.

Statement of the Problem:

There are many factors that influence an individual's job satisfaction such as skill variety, task significance, job feedback; role variables i.e. whether there is any role ambiguity, role conflict which are a part of the job itself. Other factors such as pay, gender, cultural and ethnic differences, personality characteristics-self-concept, self-efficacy etc. are part of extrinsic factors that affect job satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of the study is as follows

- To measure the employees job satisfaction level in SPS Chilling Centre
- To study the employee's perception towards organization.
- To study the attitude of employees towards their work.
- To identify the factors that motivates the employee
- To give suggestion for the growth & perspective of the company.

Hypotheses of the Study:

It means tentative generalization of the validity of which remains the tested. In short it deals with certain assumptions made in the study.

- Null Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is no significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called null hypothesis. It is denoted by Ho
- Alternative Hypothesis: A hypothesis which assumes that there is a significant difference between sample statistics and population parameter is called alternative hypothesis. It is denoted by H1

Research Design and Methodology:

The research done is a descriptive study involving survey and fact finding enquiry. The major purpose of the study is description of the state of affairs as it exists in the present organization, SPS Chilling Centre. The data and records of the employees are also examined to understand the problem well. A systematic research with structured and specified steps in specified sequence was designed and is as follows:

- Step 1: The objective is specified with sufficient precision to ensure that data collected is relevant.
- Step 2: The data collection method to be used is questionnaires, interviews and observations. While designing data collection procedure, adequate safeguards against bias and unreliability are ensured
- Step 3: The questions are prepared in a clear, understandable manner.

Data Sources:

- Primary Data: Primary data are those, which are collected for the first time. They are original in character. The data collected by the investigator for the first time for their own use is usually classed as primary data.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data are those that have already been collected by others. These are usually available in journals, periodicals, dailies, research publication official records etc., they may either be

available in published form or in an unpublished form. When it is not possible to collect the data by primary method, the investigator may make use of this method

Statistical Tools Applied:

Statistical tools like simple percentage and chi square used in the compilation and computation of data.

(i) Percentage Analysis, (ii) Chi-Square Test, (iii) Correlation Analysis

The primary data had was collected from the samples from various areas and have been properly arranged, edited and tabulated in a systematic format and analyzed by using appropriate statistical tools. A bipartite correlation and liner regression analysis were carryout using SPSS

Conclusion:

The following are the most important factors which have lead to job satisfaction in my organization among the employees; this is found through factor analysis. These are:

- Team work
- Commitment
- Culture
- Communication
- Training

The following are the five factors which needs to be worked on:

- Delegation
- Job Design
- Opportunities
- Rewards
- Leadership

The study did not observe any differences between marketers and those working in an office for training satisfaction. The survey found an increase in overall training satisfaction and employee job satisfaction with increase in respondents age; Analyzing job rank, overall satisfaction with training is seen to be increasing with respondents job rank, a similar behavior can be witnessed for Job satisfaction that also show a surge with rise in rank.

References:

1. Beer, M. 1964. Organizational size and job satisfaction. *The Academy of Management Journal* 7(1): 34-44.
2. Benke, R. L. Jr. and J. G. Rhode. 1980. The job satisfaction of higher level employees in large certified public accounting firms. *Accounting, Organizations and Society* 5(2): 187-201.
3. Bhagat, R. S. 1982. Conditions under which stronger job performance-job satisfaction relationships may be observed: A closer look at two situational contingencies. *The Academy of Management Journal* 25(4): 772-789.
4. Bullen, M. L. and E. G. Flamholtz. 1985. A theoretical and empirical investigation of job satisfaction and intended turnover in the large CPA firm. *Accounting, Organizations and Society* 10(3): 287-302.
5. Burke, R. J. and D. S. Wilcox. 1969. Effects of different patterns and degrees of openness in superior-subordinate communication on subordinate job satisfaction. *The Academy of Management Journal* 12(3): 319-326.
6. Carpenter, C. G. and R. H. Strawser. 1971. A study of the job satisfaction of academic accountants. *The Accounting Review* (July): 509-518.
7. Velmurugan, B., R. P. Nivethigha, and C. Gnanaprakasam. "Journal Homepage:-www.journalijar.com."